

BILINGUALISM TOWARDS ENGLISH LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT

Jayvie J. Dumaat, Charles Justine S. Hontemara, John Alfred A. Inson,
Chery Mae C. Inting, Mona Marie C. Mangco, Jessa Faith B. Tuyor
Billy O. Cosares, Ed.D.

*Bohol Wisdom School College of Education
CPG North Avenue, Tagbilaran City, Bohol, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the role of bilingualism in the language development of Senior High School students at Bohol Wisdom School, which integrates Filipino and Chinese cultures. Bilingualism, the ability to manage two languages, is known to enhance cognitive functions and educational outcomes. Despite the Philippines' high English proficiency, challenges in reading comprehension and other academic areas persist. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, data was collected through a self-made survey questionnaire to examine how bilingualism influences students' motivation (drive), social interactions, and cultural awareness. The findings reveal that bilingualism significantly impacts these areas, enhancing language development and cognitive skills. Bilingual students demonstrated strong proficiency in both English and their native tongue, indicating that bilingualism positively influences language acquisition and overall cognitive development. The study recommends that educational policymakers create bilingual learning resources and training programs. School administrators should design effective bilingual education programs, while guidance counselors, parents, and students should actively support and engage in bilingual learning activities. Future research should explore the long-term impacts of bilingual education, specific teaching methods, and the role of technology in promoting bilingualism. This study provides valuable insights for enhancing educational strategies and contributes to a broader understanding of bilingualism's role in language development.

Keywords: *Bilingualism, Cognitive Functions, Educational Outcomes, Language Development*

INTRODUCTION

Language, a system of spoken, manual, or written symbols, is a distinctive human trait that transcends geographical boundaries. In the realm of bilingualism, individuals adeptly managing two languages experience cognitive benefits, enhancing executive functions through constant use (Bialystok, 2017).

In the Philippines, bilingualism poses particular challenges, especially with the predominant use of English in higher education (Department Order No. 25, s. 1974). The 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) reported that the Philippines scored the lowest in Reading Comprehension among 79 countries and the second lowest in Science and Mathematics, highlighting a crisis in education (Parojenog & Pabalan, 2024). This paradoxically low performance raises questions about the efficacy of bilingual education in a country known for its English proficiency. Academicians note the difficulties students face when studying both their mother tongue and English simultaneously.

Bohol Wisdom School provides a unique context for studying bilingualism. The coexistence of Filipino and Chinese cultures allows Senior High School students to pursue academic interests with a significant emphasis on language development. Despite this focus, more needs to be known regarding the role of bilingualism in language development.

Throughout history, people have learned languages beyond their native tongue to connect with different cultures. While anyone can learn additional languages, it is crucial to use them for genuine communication. As the world becomes increasingly globalized, bilingualism—communicating fluently in another language—has become more common.

In an interconnected and multicultural world, bilingualism's role in language development has garnered considerable attention. Proficiency in two languages has been linked to cognitive benefits, enhanced linguistic abilities, and overall cognitive flexibility. Researchers have noted that bilingual individuals demonstrate cognitive advantages over monolinguals, particularly in tasks requiring control systems necessary for proficient language performance (Kroll et al., 2012; Cummins, 2003).

Heritage language speakers, a unique group of bilinguals, typically show more advanced outcomes than second language learners due to their early exposure to a minority language at home (Montrul, 2018; Chang, 2016). Parents often use code-switching to support bilingual language acquisition, helping infants understand and learn vocabulary (Kremin et al., 2022). This practice reflects the social interface between language processing, cognition, and the brain (Kaan et al., 2020).

Early bilingualism, whether simultaneous or sequential, involves acquiring two languages from birth or early childhood, respectively (De Houwer, 2017). Bilingual advantages are thought to result from cognitive control training in dual language use, where both languages are active in the brain (Hoshino & Thierry, 2011; Kroll et al., 2008).

Among fluent bilinguals, both languages continually interact, even in contexts where only one is used (Bialystok, 2017). Adults have reported that bilingualism supports relationships with family and friends and increases access to hobbies, educational, and employment opportunities (Nolte et al., 2021).

Given these factors, this study aims to address this gap by exploring the impact of bilingualism on the language development of Senior High School students at Bohol Wisdom School. It seeks to understand the language challenges faced by these students, thereby benefiting educators in designing tailored strategies and contributing to a broader understanding of bilingualism in Philippine language development.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study was to determine the role of bilingualism towards language development among Senior High School Students at Bohol Wisdom School.

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the respondents' profiles in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex; and
 - 1.2 languages spoken?
2. What is the role of bilingualism along:
 - 2.1 drive;
 - 2.2 social; and
 - 2.3 culture?
3. What are the respondents' level of language development in terms of:
 - 3.1 drive;
 - 3.2 social; and
 - 3.3 culture?
4. Is there a significant relationship between bilingualism and language development?
5. What action plan could be proposed based on the findings of this study?

METHODOLOGY

This section focused on the methodology that was utilized in the conduct of the study. This also outlined the research design, the procedure that was followed, the process of collecting the data and the analysis. During the collection process, the ethical consideration was also discussed.

Research Design

The researchers used a descriptive-correlational research design, which was suited for achieving the study's goals and objectives. The Descriptive research design was used to describe the level of influence of the factors affecting the role of bilingualism on language development. Meanwhile, the Correlational research design was applied to

determine if there is a significant relationship between the two variables. Furthermore, a self-made survey questionnaire was distributed to the respondents.

Research Environment and Research Participants

The researchers used a descriptive-correlational research design, which was suited for achieving the study's goals and objectives. The Descriptive research design was used to describe the level of influence of the factors affecting the role of bilingualism on language development. Meanwhile, the Correlational research design was applied to determine if there is a significant relationship between the two variables. Furthermore, a self-made survey questionnaire was distributed to the respondents.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study was a self-made survey questionnaire. The researchers formulated the questionnaire, which was given to the respondents. The questionnaire was divided into three categories that represent factors in language development.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents
(N=184)

Sections	No. of Respondents
12 - Justice	36
12 - Charity	34
12 - Loyalty	33
12 - Stewardship	33
12 - Compassion	27
12 - Humility	21
TOTAL	184

Moreover, the findings and discussions of related studies and articles aided the formulation of questions for the self-made questionnaire. Finally, pilot testing was first conducted on Senior High School students at Bohol Wisdom School to assess the validity and consistency of the questionnaire.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers requested approval from the research adviser and the Bohol Wisdom School High School principal before surveying the Senior High School students. With their approval, the researchers distributed questionnaires and answer sheets to each classroom in the Senior High School Department. The respondents were asked to answer the questionnaire honestly to ensure the validity of the results. Finally, all data that was gathered from the questionnaire was kept confidential.

Data Analysis

To determine the respondents' profile on age, gender, and year level, the percentage formula was applied.

Where:	
P	= Percentage
F	= Frequency
N	= Number of cases

To determine the role of bilingualism and language development, the weighted mean formula was utilized.

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

W	=	weighted average
n	=	number of terms to be average
w_i	=	weights applied to x values
x_i	=	data values to be averaged

To determine the significant relationship between the role of bilingualism and language development, the Pearson Moment Product Coefficient Correlation was used.

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{(n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2)(n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)}}$$

Where:

r	=	correlation coefficient
n	=	number of data pairs
$\sum xy$	=	the sum of the product of first and second variable
$\sum x$	=	the sum of the first variable
$\sum y$	=	the sum of the second variable
$\sum x^2$	=	the sum of the square of the first variable
$\sum y^2$	=	the sum of the square of the second variable

<u>Interval coefficient</u>	<u>Relationship level</u>
0.80-1.000	Very Strong
0.60-0.799	Strong
0.40-0.599	Moderate
0.20-0.399	Weak
0.00-0.199	Very weak

RESULTS

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of data to answer the problems raised in the study. The first part entails the profile of the respondents namely: sex and languages spoken. The second part reveals the students' profile on Bilingualism on Drive, Social and Culture. The third part reveals the students' profile on Language Development on Drive, Social and Culture. Lastly, the fourth part shows the significant relationship that exists between bilingualism and language development.

Figure 2. Respondents' Profile on Sex (184)

Figure 2 shows the respondents' profile on sex. As reflected, it revealed that 57% of them were females and 43% were males. This implies that there were more female respondents who answered the survey questionnaire.

Figure 3. Respondents' Profile on Languages Spoken (N=184)

Figure 3 presents the respondents' languages spoken. As shown, the English language got the highest percentage of 36%, while others obtained the lowest percentage of 3%. This implies that most of the respondents can speak the English Language in the survey conducted.

Zubkov (2020) states that English is taught and learned as a second language or as a foreign language in educational institutions worldwide. This implies a significant level of proficiency or familiarity with the language as English is widely taught and learned in educational setting. This also shows that people acknowledge the fact that learning the English language is the key in the present age.

**Table 2
Respondents' Role of Bilingualism on Drive
(N=184)**

Items	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank
1. I watch tutorials on how to properly construct sentences and pronounce words.	2.58	S	5
2. I read books to better enhance my language skills.	2.93	S	3
3. I ask advice from proficient English speakers to enhance my language skills.	2.81	S	4
4. I am motivated to understand the culture and people which also use the languages that I speak.	3.15	S	2
5. I aim to become a proficient speaker in both my native language and the English language.	3.5	A	1
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.99	S	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Always
2.51 – 3.25 Sometimes

1.76 – 2.5 Rarely
1.00 – 1.75 Never

Table 2 presents the respondents' perception on Bilingualism on Drive. Item number 5, "I aim to become a proficient speaker in both my native language and the English language," received the highest weighted mean of 3.5. Meanwhile, item number 1, "I watch tutorials on how to properly construct sentences and pronounce words," received the lowest weighted mean of 2.58. The overall weighted mean obtained is 2.99 with the descriptive value of "Sometimes".

This implies that individuals may not consistently exhibit high levels of motivation and drive towards language learning. Despite the strong aspiration to become proficient bilingual speakers, there may be fluctuations in motivation levels.

According to Nuraeni and Aisyah (2020), only a few are motivated by intrinsic factors such as the need or desire to excel, feel good about oneself, achieve a goal, or fulfill a part of oneself. This means that there is only a small portion of the population that are naturally motivated to achieve certain things.

Table 3
Respondents' Role of Bilingualism on Social (N=184)

Items	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank
1. I can use the languages that I know in conversations with people who use the same languages.	3.55	A	2
2. I can switch languages depending on the topic and the situation with ease.	3.46	A	3
3. I can speak with my peers using my native language and the English language.	3.64	A	1
4. I often find myself code- switching or using my native tongue and the English language alternately when talking with my peers.	3.44	A	4
5. I can write letters with proper grammar usage and can understand them as well in both languages that I speak.	3.43	A	5
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.50	A	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Always
2.51 – 3.25 Sometimes

1.76 – 2.5 Rarely
1.00 – 1.75 Never

Table 3 exhibits the respondents' profile on bilingualism under the social factor. It was found that item 3, "I can speak with my peers using my native language and the English language," obtained the highest value of 3.64. Meanwhile, item 5, "I can write letters with proper grammar usage and can understand them as well in both languages that I speak," got the lowest value of 3.43. The overall weighted mean obtained is 3.50 with a descriptive value of "Always."

This implies a high level of confidence in using both languages for social purposes. In simpler terms, the survey suggests people feel comfortable talking to friends in both languages.

Table 5
Summary on the Role of Bilingualism (N=184)

Role of Bilingualism	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank
Drive	2.99	Sometimes	3
Social	3.50	Always	1
Culture	3.34	Always	2
Average Weighted Mean	3.27	Always	

Table 5 shows the summary of the role of bilingualism on drive, social and culture. "Social" obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.50. In contrast, "drive" garnered the lowest weighted mean of 2.99. It has an overall average weighted mean of 3.31 described as "Always."

In one way of saying, bilingualism will most likely have a conclusive influence on bilinguals' motivation to learn more about the languages that they speak, their knowledge on the culture of these languages, and the way they socialize.

Ünveren et al. (2019) cited that bilinguals' linguistic and intercultural repertoires are larger. This means that bilingualism can give several advantages, significantly increasing people's potential to excel, may it be in language learning or in other fields.

Table 6
Respondents' Level of Language Development on Drive (N=184)

Items	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank
1. I self-correct myself whenever I can spot errors using the English language.	3.33	HD	1
2. I aim to ace my English tests.	3.18	D	4
3. I converse with my peers in school using the English language.	3.00	D	5
4. I train myself to watch English movies without the help of subtitles.	3.26	HD	3
5. I strictly adhere to the grammatical rules of the English language.	3.32	HD	2
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.22	D	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Highly Developed 1.76 – 2.50 Less Developed
 2.51 – 3.25 Developed 1.00 – 1.75 Not Developed

Table 6 reveals the level of Language Development. It revealed that the item 1, "I self-correct myself whenever I can spot errors using the English language," obtained the highest value of 3.33. Meanwhile, statement 3 "I converse with my peers in school using the English language," obtained the lowest value of 3.00. The overall weighted mean obtained is 3.22 with a descriptive value of "Developed."

This entails that the learners are motivated by internal satisfaction in language development.

Yue et al. (2022) found that among other various factors, the learners' motivation influences effective learning and it can be identified as one of the most important factors in successful language learning. This implies that motivation is a key factor to be targeted to expand learning and the students should be motivated on a consistent basis to achieve better learning outcomes.

Table 7
Respondents' Level of Language Development on Social (N=184)

Items	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank
1. I can speak with native English speakers or people adept in using the English language without them slowing down or simplifying their speech for me.	3.32	HD	2
2. I can crack jokes and word plays using the English language.	3.26	HD	4
3. I can understand slang words when conversing with people who use the English language and responding accordingly.	3.53	HD	1
4. I can use idiomatic expressions in conversations which use the English language.	3.18	D	5
5. I am confident in conversing with someone using the English language.	3.28	HD	3
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.31	HD	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Highly Developed
2.51 – 3.25 Developed

1.76 – 2.50 Less Developed
1.00 – 1.75 Not Developed

Table 7 reveals the respondents' perception on Language Development on Social. Item number 3, "I can understand slang words when conversing with people who use English Language and respond accordingly" obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.53 with a descriptive value of "Highly Developed". In contrast, item number 4, "I can use idiomatic expressions in conversation which use the English language" garnered the lowest weighted mean of 3.18 with a descriptive value of "Developed". The set of items pertaining to the influence of language development on Social got an overall weighted mean of 3.31 with a descriptive value of "Highly Developed."

This implies that respondents exhibited a strong ability to socialize confidently using the English language. Zukefli, N. N., & Subramaniam, V. (2018).

Zukefli and Subramaniam (2018) mentioned that language serves as a mixture of indispensable abilities for the purpose of communicating, speaking and interacting with each other. This means that language development is heavily influenced through the way we socialize, since its nature and purpose is to fuel interactions and communication among people.

Table 8
Respondents' Level of Language Development on Culture (N=184)

Items	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Value	Rank
1. I am aware that my native tongue and the English language has its own roots and culture.	2.97	D	5
2. I can understand other cultures through the English language.	3.29	HD	1
3. I can interact with others using the English language.	3.18	D	3
4. I can understand and follow directions given to me in English language.	3.24	D	2
5. I can easily help translate for others from the languages that I know.	3.12	D	4
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.16	D	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Highly Developed
2.51 – 3.25 Developed

1.76 – 2.50 Less Developed
1.00 – 1.75 Not Developed

Table 8 reveals the respondents' perception on Language Development on Culture. Item number 2, "I can understand other cultures through the English language" obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.29 with a descriptive value of "Highly Developed". In contrast, item number 1, "I am aware that my native tongue and the English language has its own roots and culture" garnered the lowest weighted mean of 2.97 with a descriptive value of "Developed".

The set of items pertaining the influence of language development on culture got an overall weighted mean of 3.16 with a descriptive value of "Developed." This means that the respondents exhibited an adequate foundation in understanding and engaging with cultures through language.

Similarly, Alyasery et al. (2018) cites that language has a dual character: both as a tool of communication and a carrier of culture. This shows that it serves a dual purpose, to act as a means of communication and a vessel for cultural expression as the respondents are in a process that goes beyond mere language acquisition including cultural awareness and appreciation.

Table 9
Summary on the Level of Language Development (N=184)

Level of Language Development	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Mean	Rank
On Drive	3.22	Developed	2
On Social	3.31	Highly Developed	1
On Culture	3.16	Developed	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.23	Developed	

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 Highly Developed
2.51 – 3.25 Developed

1.76 – 2.50 Less Developed
1.00 – 1.75 Not Developed

Table 9 shows the summary on the level of language development. “Social” obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.31. Meanwhile, “culture” garnered the lowest weighted mean of 3.16. Overall, it has an average weighted mean of 3.23 with a descriptive value of “Developed.”

This indicates that the respondents showed a respectable language development but falls short of being considered as exceptional or advanced.

According to Pirbhai-Illich & Martin et al. (2019) language development can be elevated from acquiring grammar and cultural facts to gaining sociocultural knowledge and awareness. This suggests that language development can be observed and is relative to several factors including cultural awareness and the way we socialize.

Table 10
Significant Relationship Between the Role of Bilingualism and Level of Language Development (N=184)

Relationship	Computed r	Critical r value	P - value	Interpretation	Decision
Bilingualism vs Language Development	0.7125	±0.13675	<.00001	Strong positive correlation	Reject H_0

Table 10 shows the significant relationship between bilingualism and language development. Data revealed that Computed r value of 0.7125 is greater than the critical r value of 0.13675 and a computed p value of <0.00001. The value indicated that the null hypothesis is to be rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between bilingualism and language development. Furthermore, the value indicated that the relationship is strongly positive.

This implies that individuals who are bilingual tend to demonstrate more advanced language skills and proficiency compared to monolingual individuals, underscoring the cognitive and linguistic benefits of being bilingual.

This is connected with what Tribushinina, Boz, Aalbers, and Blom (2024) have stated that Bilingual development may be associated with additional benefits, including cognitive advantages. One type of bilingual advantage may lie in foreign language learning. This means that those individuals who are able to use two languages will be more likely to succeed in learning another language than those monolinguals.

DISCUSSION

Findings

Based on the analysis of the data, the following findings emerged:

Respondents' Profile

On Sex. Data showed that that majority of the respondents were females.

On Languages Spoken. Among other languages, the English language was found to be the most spoken language.

Role of Bilingualism:

On Drive. The data shows that the respondents' drive do sometimes influence their motivation to learn different languages, where some are motivated to do ways to learn and adapt new languages and others are not, for everyone does not have the same level of motivation.

On Social. It was found out that the respondents' socialization always affects the way they interact using the languages that they know. This also shows that bilinguals are always open to conversations which may enable them to use their native tongue and the English language.

On Culture. It was revealed that bilingualism helps the respondents to broaden their knowledge and understanding about other cultures. Bilingualism can also bridge people to connect with each other and can start a relationship with people from various cultures.

On Summary. Data suggests that the role of bilingualism has a significant impact on motivation, socialization, and cultural awareness. Bilingualism not only encourages ongoing language learning but also boosts individuals to adapt in social contexts and fosters a deeper understanding and respect for diverse cultures.

Levels of Language Development:

On Drive. The data shows that the respondents' language development was developed; the respondents are aiming to learn and improve their skills and ability in languages through self-drive, where they are motivated to develop their language more by self-correct, self-training and adhering to some language grammatical rules.

On Social. Data revealed that the respondents' level of language development is highly developed; the respondents exhibited a strong ability to use the English language. In socializing, the respondents were confident in their ability to converse with other people.

On Culture. Data revealed that respondent's level of language development on culture is developed; The respondents are clearly affected by their surroundings. Fact is that the environment is culturally diverse, so everyone wants to be culturally literate and establish unity in order to avoid any squabble. Respondents aim to develop their languages at the same time they can be of help in creating the environment they sought.

On Summary. Data revealed that the level of language development of the respondents is highly developed. The respondents answered exceptionally in factors that determined their development such as drive, social, and culture. This shows that majority of the respondents are adept English language speakers.

On Relationship. There is a significant relationship that exists between the role of bilingualism on drive, social, and culture with the level of language development.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that there is a significant relationship between the role of bilingualism and the level of language development. This means that bilingualism can influence or stimulate language development in a favorable way.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from the findings accumulated, it is recommended that:

1. The Secretary of the Department of Education may collaborate with language experts to create bilingual learning resources and national guidelines. Public awareness campaigns can highlight the benefits of bilingualism in education, while funding and support can be directed towards training educators in bilingual teaching methods.
2. School Administrator may design bilingual learning programs, like dual language immersion. Working with teachers, they can ensure the curriculum effectively integrates both languages and content. By collecting data on student progress and

program effectiveness, administrators can continuously improve the bilingual learning experience for all students.

3. Guidance Office Personnel may provide valuable resources, connect students with specialists if needed, and collaborate with teachers to ensure learners receive proper academic and social- emotional support in both languages. Creating a comprehensive support system will empower them to thrive in both languages and cultures.

4. Parents may continue using the native language at home while supporting English development. Exploring bilingual children's literature and media can provide shared learning experiences. Engaging with schools strengthens collaboration in supporting the child's bilingual journey.

5. Students may actively participate in activities that leverage their skills, strategically code- switch for clarity, and seek opportunities to connect with other bilingual learners. Embracing the challenges and rewards of bilingualism empowers them to excel in English language learning.

6. Future researchers may investigate the long-term impact of bilingual education programs, study the effectiveness of specific bilingual teaching methods, and explore the role of technology in promoting bilingual learning and cross-cultural communication.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm came to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. Researchers declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

PROPOSED ACTION PLAN FOR BILINGUALISM TOWARDS ENGLISH LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT

Rationale

In today's increasingly interconnected world, proficiency in English has invaluable advantages for communication, education, and career advancement. However, for individuals growing up in bilingual environments, developing excellent English language abilities might be a unique challenge. Students ought to have unrestricted access to assistance they require, particularly when it comes to their language skills. In this case, teachers should include implementing bilingual reading projects and activities that use both languages to improve comprehension or offering focused assistance to bilingual kids

who are struggling with specific areas of English. With this knowledge of the impact of bilingualism on the development of English language skills, the study's proposed action plan aims to offer suggestions and recommendations on how to assist educators, parents, administrators, and learners in realizing the benefits and necessity of bilingualism in language development.

Objectives

After the implementation of the proposed improvement plan, the research aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. encourages students to feel confident and display improved proficiency in both languages specifically, English.
2. develops deeper appreciation for both languages and fosters a sense of belongingness and identity within their school environment.
3. integrates students the cultural elements of both languages into educational materials and activities leading to deeper understanding in cultural context.
4. improves language skills enable them to help in their studies.
5. gives awareness to students about the advantages of bilingual people within their school environment.
6. ensures that the common language difficulties encountered by the students will be dealt with by the activities implemented.

Mechanics of Implementation

The researchers shall present the proposed plan to the Head of the Administrative Team and to the Principal of the High School Department for approval after the examining panel has subjected it to refinement. Upon approval, the researchers will forward the proposal to the DOH, DepEd, and to the Office of the City Mayor where further clarification will be provided.

Schedule of Implementation

The implementation of the program of proposal shall commence once permission is granted to the researchers by the authorities in charge.

Monitoring and Evaluating

To ensure the strict implementation of the proposed plan, the researchers would adapt a periodic monitoring and evaluation to determine effectiveness in its results. This is to identify if there are areas of concern that need further improvements in which an immediate response would be expected from the researchers.

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